

FETAL MICROCHIMERISM: IMMUNOLOGICAL IMPLICATIONS IN AUTOIMMUNE DISORDERS

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ABSTRACT

Autoimmune diseases exhibit a higher prevalence among women beyond the age of 30, with a significant proportion occurring in women who have experienced at least one pregnancy. While the gestational period involves a shared circulation between the mother and the fetus for nine months, extensive research has elucidated the presence of fetal cells within maternal blood even years after the pregnancy. Although these phenomena are now widely acknowledged in the scientific community, the persistence and potential consequences of fetal DNA within the maternal circulation remain topics of ongoing debate and limited comprehension.

This research paper aims to delve deeper into the intricate relationship between maternal and fetal DNA, its enduring impact on the body, and its potential connection to autoimmune diseases in the field of immunology

Keywords: Fetal microchimerism, Systemic sclerosis, Autoimmune.

1. Introduction:

The immune system operates as a meticulously regulated mechanism, tirelessly safeguarding the body throughout one's entire life against foreign entities, including microbes and anomalous cells. Despite its constant activity and exposure to self-antigens, the immune system remains non-responsive to them. However, there are instances when these processes malfunction, leading to harm of different tissues.

Autoimmunity arises when the body generates autoantibodies and immunologically capable T lymphocytes directed against its own tissues. When the mechanisms responsible for maintaining self-tolerance break down, the resulting conditions are classified as autoimmune disorders, and the phenomenon is referred to as autoimmunity [1].

Systemic sclerosis, also known as scleroderma, is a complex and chronic autoimmune connective tissue disorder with a heterogeneous clinical presentation, it is characterized by abnormal immune system activation and widespread fibrosis or thickening of the skin, as well as various internal organs such as the gastrointestinal tract, lungs, heart, and blood vessels. The disease's exact cause remains unclear, and its management typically involves a multidisciplinary approach to address the diverse range of symptoms and complications that may arise [2]

Microchimerism is a fascinating biological phenomenon where small numbers of cells or DNA from one individual can be found in another individual's body. This exchange of genetic material typically occurs during pregnancy and childbirth, although it can also happen through blood transfusions and organ transplantation [3].

Microchimerism is particularly significant in women because it can involve the presence of cells or DNA from their children in various tissues and organs. There are two primary types of microchimerism in women: fetal Microchimerism: During pregnancy, fetal cells and DNA can enter the mother's bloodstream and establish themselves in her body, where they may persist for many years or even a lifetime. fetal cells can be

detected in a mother's blood, bone marrow, and various organs. This unique exchange of genetic material may have implications for the mother's health and immune system [4]. Maternal Microchimerism: Conversely, mothers can also pass their cells to their children during pregnancy and breastfeeding. This transfer of maternal cells to the child may play a role in the child's immune system development and potentially offer protective benefits [3].

An intriguing question in the realm of reproductive biology and immunology is whether fetal cells and DNA endure as persistent inhabitants within women's tissues long after pregnancy has concluded. This question not only bears implications for our understanding of the long-term interplay between maternal and fetal cells, but also the potential impacts on maternal health, and its broader relevance in the context of immunological and medical research.

This meta-analysis is based on the results of three papers in the field of immunology and oncology. The first paper [A] discusses the presence of fetal DNA and cells in skin lesions and peripheral blood of women with scleroderma, while the second paper [B] mentions the presence of fetal cells in the heart of women who gave birth to at least one son. The third paper [C] dives into HLA-compatibility between mothers with scleroderma and their children while also detecting fetal cell DNA in peripheral blood. Our goal is to further understand the potential connection between fetal cell DNA, microchimerism and autoimmunity, address the possible implications of this complicated relation and how it can help us in different medical fields.

2. Methods:

Subjects:

2.1. In the skin lesion cells study of women with systemic sclerosis, 69 women had their DNA extracted from peripheral blood cells while 25 healthy women had their DNA extracted by a procedure involving sodium chloride-ethanol precipitation. 19 women with systemic sclerosis of ≤ 18 months also had a biopsy of active skin lesions. While the control groups had DNA extraction from 7 women with osteoarthritis and 61 of

their female relatives. 9 women with eosinophilic myalgia syndrome, 2 women with eosinophilic fasciitis, 1 woman with polymyositis.

2.2 The subjects of the extra cardiac male cardiomyocytes study are 2 non-pregnant women who underwent heart transplantation. The first patient was 59 year old at the time of transplantation, had 5 pregnancies, 1 son, male twins, 1 daughter and 1 miscarriage. The interval between her most recent male pregnancy and operation is 24 years. The second patient was 47 year old and had 2 pregnancies resulting in 2 sons, the interval between the most recent son and the operation is 15 years. Idiopathic dilated cardiomyopathy was diagnosed 16 years and 13 years after delivery respectively. The control group includes 2 men and 2 women who had no history of pregnancy.

2.3 The subjects of the microchimerism and HLA-compatibility investigation involved two distinct groups, with no overlap between them due to their differing study requirements.

The male DNA quantification analysis encompassed 40 women, each of whom had at least one son. Among these participants, 17 had systemic sclerosis, 7 were healthy sisters of scleroderma patients, and 16 were unrelated healthy women. Notably, all patients with systemic sclerosis exhibited internal organ involvement.

In the HLA compatibility study, a total of 136 subjects from 21 different families participated. This group comprised 21 patients, 10 fathers and their 47 children, 15 mothers, and 8 fathers of patients, 9 siblings with 22 children, and 4 additional individuals (the latter group was used to validate haplotype assignments and confirm homozygosity). Five individuals were excluded from the study due to a history of blood transfusions, and one participant was excluded for having a fraternal twin. The control group for this study consisted of 130 subjects from 32 different families, which included 32 controls, 7 fathers and their 58 children, 26 mothers, and 2 fathers of controls, as well as 5 other individuals.

Data collection:

The first study: The history of pregnancy in the convenient group is 2 out of 69 women had at least 1 son, the remaining pregnancy histories were not known. The control group that included 7 women with osteoarthritis and 61 of their relatives, 29% of them had sons, 15% had daughters, and 31% were nulliparous, the history of the remainder is unknown. Out of the 12 women with with eosinophilic myalgia syndrome, eosinophilic fasciitis and polymyositis, only 1 woman has

had multiple pregnancies, the histories of the remainder is unknown.

The second study:

The 2 non-pregnant women underwent heart transplantation due to idiopathic dilated cardiomyopathy. And neither had a blood transfusion, autoimmune disorders or peripartum cardiomyopathy before.

Laboratory tests:

1. While studying skin lesions in women with systemic sclerosis, different methods were used including: Polymerase-chain-reaction analysis for Y-chromosome-positive cells, Sequence Analysis of the PCR-Amplified Product, Fluorescence in Situ Hybridization of Peripheral-Blood Cells, and Fluorescence in Situ Hybridization of Paraffin-Embedded Skin-Biopsy Specimens.

2. The second study used 3 methods: Real-time Polymerase-chain-reaction analysis, Combined Immunohistochemical and FISH Analysis, and Histocompatibility Studies.

3. The third study comprised two experiments. In the first experiment, the Y-chromosome served as a marker for quantifying presumed fetal-cell DNA equivalents. The samples were tested using PCR with a primary target of the long arm of the Y-chromosome (Y-49a-06:5'). The results were expressed as the count of male cell DNA equivalents present within a 16ml sample derived from peripheral blood.

The second experiment involved the detection of HLA class II alleles in heparinized whole blood samples through DNA typing. Specifically, sequence-specific oligonucleotide-probe typing was employed to identify HLA class II alleles at the DRB1, DQA1, and DQB1 loci. The obtained results were subsequently compared with those of a control group using non-parametric Kolmogorov-Smirnov and permutation testing and permutation testing with overall scores.

3. Results:

3.1 The first paper:

Polymerase-chain-reaction analyses of peripheral-blood and skin DNA showed the presence of Y-chromosome-specific DNA in 11 out of 19 women with active skin lesions and systemic sclerosis in 18 months or less (58%). However the 68 women with osteoarthritis or their relatives had none. The DNA extracted from active skin lesions of women with eosinophilia myalgia syndrome, eosinophilic fasciitis or polymyositis came negative too. (Chart 1)

Chart 1: Y-chromosome-specific DNA detection results using PCR analysis of both peripheral blood and skin DNA

SSc: systemic sclerosis, OS: osteoarthritis, E,E,P: eosinophilia myalgia syndrome, Eosinophilic fasciitis, Polymyositis.

Fluorescence in situ hybridization of peripheral-blood cells found Y-chromosome sequences in CD3, CD14 and CD45 in three women with systemic sclerosis who had at least one son. While the healthy women and the women with systemic sclerosis who were never pregnant tested negative for the Y-chromosome.

Fluorescence in situ hybridization of skin-biopsy specimens found that all seven women with systemic sclerosis whose specimen contained y-chromosome sequences as detected by PCR and whose skin-biopsy

specimens were tested by in situ hybridization. The majority of Y-chromosome-containing nucleated cells were found within the inflammatory cell infiltrates localized in the extracellular matrix of the deep dermis. The healthy women showed no signs of Y-chromosome containing nucleated cells.

3.2 The second paper:

Real-time Polymerase-chain-reaction found the presence of at least 1 male cell out of every 10⁴ female cells in the heart of both women (table 1)

Table 1:

Results of Real-time PCR in both female patients and the control group.

	X- chromosome	Y- chromosome
Patient 1	0.25%	0.25%
Patient 2	0.20%	0.20%
Male hearts	75%	75%
Female hearts	86%	-

FISH analysis of X- and Y-chromosome-specific DNA sequence in combination with alpha-actin immunohisto-chemistry came positive in both women, with 0.25% cells in the first patient, and 0.20% cells in the second. The cells were located as singles and not as clusters.

patient-Son histocompatibility found a strong and high HLA compatibility between both parents & their sons. The first patient showed a high HLA class II compatibility with her 3 sons while the second patient has a high HLA class I compatibility with her sons.

3.3 The third study:

Detection of mean cell DNA equivalent in 16 subjects from control group showed 0.38 male cells per 16ml of blood. From these 16 women, all had one to three son, some had daughters, three had fatal loss in the first trimester and one had a blood transfusion. While 17 patients with systemic sclerosis showed 11.1

male cell DNA equivalents in blood, all subjects had one to five sons, some had daughters, six had fatal losses, two received a blood transfusion before systemic sclerosis onset while four after the onset. All women experienced the onset of scleroderma following their final childbirth, with the exception of two individuals who developed the condition between their sixth and seventh childbirths, and another individual between her first and second childbirths.

All 17 subjects were taking different drugs for their condition such as D-penicillamine, methotrexate, prednisone, NSAIDs; no correlation between the drug intake and male DNA concentration was found. Of the 7 sisters of the systemic sclerosis patients, only two had a higher male DNA concentration compared to those of the control group; with a mean male cell DNA equivalent of 1.3, all sisters had from one to three sons. (Table 2)

Table 2

Results of quantitative tests for male DNA in blood

	Healthy women	Women with Systemic sclerosis	Healthy sisters of patients
Male cell DNA equivalents, mean & range	0.38 (0-2)	11.1 (0-61)	1.3 (0-5)
Age of the mother	45 years 25-61	46 years 33-64	44 years 26-69
Years since birth of the youngest son	15.4 years	18.5 years	17.1 years
Age of sons	20.4 years 0.2-40	18.4 years 0.2-44	22.4 years 4-46

The HLA study only included women with living children who were willing to participate fully. To properly study the HLA compatibility between mother and child, HLA has to either be identical or homozygous. A higher proportion of women diagnosed with scleroderma had delivered at least one child compatible with HLA class II compared to the control group. The

assessment included the determination of Class II alleles, such as DRB1, DRB3, DRB4, DRB5, DQA1, and DQB1. In Stage 1 DRB1 typing, the classification corresponds to the DRB1 families DR1 to DR14, and in Stage 2 DRB1 typing, the specific DRB1 allele was identified. The DRB3, DRB4, and DRB5 loci exhibited limited polymorphism, while the most pronounced association was observed in DRB1¹. (Table 3)

Table 3

HLA-compatibility between patients and their sons

Locus	Patients with systemic sclerosis	Control group
DRB1 ₁	13 (62%)	5 (16%)
DRB1 ₂	9 (43%)	3 (9%)
DQA1	15 (71%)	12 (38%)
DQB1	13 (62%)	11 (34%)

4. Discussion:

During pregnancy, the fetus and mother are connected through the placenta, an organ that develops in the uterus to provide a link between the developing fetus and the mother's circulatory system. The placenta plays a crucial role in facilitating the exchange of nutrients, gases, and waste products between the mother and the fetus [6]. There are many hypotheses as to how cells can cross from the fetus to the mother through the placental barrier. One hypothesis suggests adhesive attachment and migration taking place across the endothelial lining of high endothelial venules in peripheral lymph nodes, as well as at the blood-brain barrier [5], while another suggests micro-ruptures in the blood channels within the placenta get micro damaged which may lead to cell exchange between fetus and mother [6]. However, the main hypothesis we currently have is that trophoblasts which are cells that originate from the developing embryo and play a crucial role in placental formation, invade maternal tissues. This invasion facilitates the transfer of fetal cells into the maternal bloodstream [7]. Fetal cells and DNA being present and persistent in the mother's body even after pregnancy is what we call fetal microchimerism.

These cells are regarded as foreign entities by the mother's immune system; a system designed to recognize and defend against foreign substances, and fetal cells carry distinct genetic markers that differentiate them from maternal cells, thus their presence can trigger an immune response [1]. The delicate balance between immune tolerance and recognition of foreign elements is crucial for a successful pregnancy and influences the complex interplay between maternal and fetal cells during gestation [3]. However the presence of fetal cell DNA in the mother's body after pregnancy is over could potentially trigger an immune response, contributing to the development or exacerbation of autoimmune conditions [1].

There's a strong correlation between fetal cells and systemic sclerosis which is a connective tissue disease. Our immune system is designed to protect the body without interfering with its normal function. However when an inflammation or a reaction is so severe or chronic, it can lead to fibrosis of different internal organs, which consequently can result in their dysfunction long term [8].

Chronic Graft-versus-Host Disease (cGVHD) is an immunological complication that can arise following allogeneic stem cell or bone marrow transplanta-

tion. In this condition, immune cells from the donor recognize the recipient's tissues as foreign and mount a prolonged attack against various organs. cGVHD often manifests beyond the initial post-transplantation period

and can affect different organs [9]. Systemic sclerosis has been compared to chronic graft-versus-host disease (cGVHD) before due to their similarities (table 4)

Table 4

Most common features between SSc and cGvHD

Features	Systemic Sclerosis	cGvHD
Sclerodactyly	+++	++
Cardiac	+	-
Pulmonary	++	+
Gastrointestinal	+++	++
Hepatic	++	+++
Renal	++	-
Myositis	++	+
Raynaud's Phenomenon	+++	+
Sicca Syndrome	++	++
Antinuclear Antibodies	+++	++
Joint involvement	++	+++

Fetal microchimerism effects the mother's body long term, and can lead to many autoimmune diseases such as systemic sclerosis and rheumatoid arthritis [1]. As women who had at least one son are more at risk due to presence of fetal DNA and their high HLA compatibility [1,3]. Fetal microchimerism has been associated with other conditions, such as breast cancer [10], cervical cancer [11], melanomas [12], Papillary thyroid cancer [12], glioblastoma [14] and preeclampsia [15] during pregnancy. Although the connection between mother and fetus is very strong and quite literally unbreakable, it can be beneficial to the mother's health long term too.

Many studies have indicated the fetal cells' ability to differentiate and migrate through the mother's body [16], as they have been found in the heart and skin tissues [A], and how they can help with tissue repair and regeneration [4]. A compelling theory suggests that fetal microchimeric cells (FMCs) present in maternal wound sites may play a role in fostering a regenerative phenotype. This could occur either through their direct involvement in the healing process or by releasing pro-regenerative molecular signals within the microenvironment of the wound [4]. Myocardial infarctions occurring in late pregnancy and the early postpartum months exhibit remarkable and fast recovery rates in comparison to other pathologies [4]. However, we should note that fetal migrating cells into the heart are not identical in structure as the mother's; unable to properly integrate, they end up forming in small clusters [B]. Another benefit of fetal cells and fetal DNA circulating in the blood is its use for early diagnosis and detection of pathologies in the prenatal period as its not intrusive and very affordable, it can also help detect early development of preeclampsia and gestational dia-

betes. Although the pros and cons of feto-maternal microchimerism are numerous, we are barely scratching the surface, and more studies need to be done to expand the field of pediatrics, gynecology, and immunology.

While our meta-analysis provides valuable insights into the pooled data from the various studies we mentioned, it is important to acknowledge certain limitations such as publication bias, small sample sizes and different designs of experiments which might affect the overall robustness of our conclusions. Future studies should aim to address these limitations through more standardized methodologies, larger sample sizes, and a rigorous assessment of potential biases. This will contribute to the ongoing refinement of our understanding in this field and improve our overall understanding of the complicated yet mesmerizing relation between mother and child.

Conclusion:

Delving into the intricacies of fetal microchimerism and its potential correlation to systemic sclerosis has been like embarking on a whimsical journey through the mysteries of the human body. Our brief exploration has uncovered fascinating connections and sparked compelling questions. Yet, this expedition into understanding the intricate relationship has merely scratched the surface. To unravel the precise mechanisms orchestrating the dance between fetal microchimerism, systemic sclerosis, and other autoimmune conditions; further research, employing standardized methodologies and larger sample sizes are needed. Moving forward, a deeper understanding of the dynamic interplay between fetal microchimerism and systemic sclerosis will not only enhance our comprehension of disease etiology but may also pave the way for personalized treatment strategies and improved patient outcomes.

References

1. Chaplin DD. Overview of the immune response. *J Allergy Clin Immunol.* 2010 Feb;125(2 Suppl 2):S3-23. doi: 10.1016/j.jaci.2009.12.980. PMID: 20176265; PMCID: PMC2923430.
2. Sobolewski P, Maślińska M, Wieczorek M, Łagun Z, Malewska A, Roszkiewicz M, Nitskovich R, Szymańska E, Walecka I. Systemic sclerosis - multidisciplinary disease: clinical features and treatment. *Reumatologia.* 2019;57(4):221-233. doi: 10.5114/reum.2019.87619. Epub 2019 Aug 31. PMID: 31548749; PMCID: PMC6753596.
3. Burlingham WJ. A lesson in tolerance--maternal instruction to fetal cells. *N Engl J Med.* 2009 Mar 26;360(13):1355-7. doi: 10.1056/NEJMcibr0810752. PMID: 19321873; PMCID: PMC2886144.
4. Sedov E, McCarthy J, Koren E, Fuchs Y. Feto-maternal microchimerism in tissue repair and tumor development. *Dev Cell.* 2022 Jun 20;57(12):1442-1452. doi: 10.1016/j.devcel.2022.05.018. Epub 2022 Jun 13. PMID: 35700729.
5. Engelhardt B. Molecular mechanisms involved in T cell migration across the blood-brain barrier. *J Neural Transm* 2006; 113:477 - 485
6. Gavin S. Dawe, Xiao Wei Tan & Zhi-Cheng Xiao (2007) Cell Migration from Baby to Mother, *Cell Adhesion & Migration*, 1:1, 19-27, DOI: 10.4161/cam.4082
7. Douglas GW, Thomas L, Carr M, Cullen NM, Morris R. Trophoblasts in circulating blood during pregnancy. *Am J Obstet Gynecol* 1959; 78:960 - 973
8. Guarino M, Tosoni A, Nebuloni M. Direct contribution of epithelium to organ fibrosis: epithelial-mesenchymal transition. *Hum Pathol.* 2009;40:1365–1376.
9. Deeg HJ, Storb R. Graft-versus-host disease: pathophysiological and clinical aspects. *Annu Rev Med.* 1984;35:11-24. doi: 10.1146/annurev.me.35.020184.000303. PMID: 6372650.
10. Gadi VK, Nelson JL. Fetal microchimerism in women with breast cancer. *Cancer Res.* 2007 Oct 1;67(19):9035-8. doi: 10.1158/0008-5472.CAN-06-4209. PMID: 17909006.
11. Cha D, Khosrotehrani K, Kim Y, Stroh H, Bianchi DW, Johnson KL. Cervical cancer and microchimerism. *Obstet Gynecol.* 2003 Oct;102(4):774-81. doi: 10.1016/s0029-7844(03)00615-x. PMID: 14551008.
12. Nguyen Huu S, Oster M, Avril MF, Boitier F, Mortier L, Richard MA, Kerob D, Maubec E, Souteyrand P, Moguelet P, Khosrotehrani K, Aractingi S. Fetal microchimeric cells participate in tumour angiogenesis in melanomas occurring during pregnancy. *Am J Pathol.* 2009 Feb;174(2):630-7. doi: 10.2353/ajpath.2009.080566. Epub 2009 Jan 15. PMID: 19147820; PMCID: PMC2630570.
13. Cirello V, Perrino M, Colombo C, Muzza M, Filopanti M, Vicentini L, Beck-Peccoz P, Fugazzola L. Fetal cell microchimerism in papillary thyroid cancer: studies in peripheral blood and tissues. *Int J Cancer.* 2010 Jun 15;126(12):2874-8. doi: 10.1002/ijc.24993. PMID: 19856309.
14. Broestl L, Rubin JB, Dahiya S. Fetal microchimerism in human brain tumors. *Brain Pathol.* 2018 Jul;28(4):484-494. doi: 10.1111/bpa.12557. Epub 2017 Oct 17. PMID: 28921714; PMCID: PMC5884742.
15. Jacobsen DP, Fjeldstad HE, Sugulle M, Johnsen GM, Olsen MB, Kanaan SB, Staff AC. Fetal microchimerism and the two-stage model of preeclampsia. *J Reprod Immunol.* 2023 Sep;159:104124. doi: 10.1016/j.jri.2023.104124. Epub 2023 Jul 25. PMID: 37541161.
16. Kara RJ, Bolli P, Karakikes I, Matsunaga I, Tripodi J, Tanweer O, Altman P, Shachter NS, Nakano A, Najfeld V, Chaudhry HW. Fetal cells traffic to injured maternal myocardium and undergo cardiac differentiation. *Circ Res.* 2012 Jan 6;110(1):82-93. doi: 10.1161/CIRCRESAHA.111.249037. Epub 2011 Nov 14. Erratum in: *Circ Res.* 2015 Nov 6;117(11):e91. PMID: 22082491; PMCID: PMC3365532.
17. A. Artlett CM, Smith JB, Jimenez SA. Identification of fetal DNA and cells in skin lesions from women with systemic sclerosis. *N Engl J Med.* 1998 Apr 23;338(17):1186-91. doi: 10.1056/NEJM199804233381704. PMID: 9554859.
18. B. Bayes-Genis A, Bellosillo B, de la Calle O, Salido M, Roura S, Ristol FS, Soler C, Martinez M, Espinet B, Serrano S, Bayes de Luna A, Cinca J. Identification of male cardiomyocytes of extracardiac origin in the hearts of women with male progeny: male fetal cell microchimerism of the heart. *J Heart Lung Transplant.* 2005 Dec;24(12):2179-83. doi: 10.1016/j.healun.2005.06.003. Epub 2005 Sep 28. PMID: 16364868.
19. C. Nelson JL, Furst DE, Maloney S, Gooley T, Evans PC, Smith A, Bean MA, Ober C, Bianchi DW. Microchimerism and HLA-compatible relationships of pregnancy in scleroderma. *Lancet.* 1998 Feb 21;351(9102):559-62. doi: 10.1016/S0140-6736(97)08357-8. PMID: 9492775.